

Infrared Spectra of Sulphathiazole Salicylaldimine (SUTSA) Metal Chelates*

R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL

Department of Chemistry, Holkar Science College, Indore (M.P.)

Manuscript received 8 October 1975; accepted 11 February 1976

The detailed I.R. data of metal sulphathiazole salicylaldimine (SUTSA) complexes has been discussed as compared to the ligand itself. The investigation confirm the structure already assigned to these complexes on the basis of physico-chemical studies.

IN a previous communication¹ we have shown by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation that sulphathiazole salicylaldimine forms complexes with Cu, Mn, Fe, and Co, the ligand metal ratio being 2:1. The complexes are highly coloured and stable. In a later communication² we have described the isolation of the complexes and on the basis of the analytical results, tentative chelate structures (IV) have been suggested.

Similarly silver-sulphathiazole-salicylaldimine complex has been studied and to which tentative structure (V) similar to (IV) has been assigned (unpublished data).

The I.R. and Raman spectra of benzene and toluene sulphonamides have been studied by Schreiber³ and Augus Lachie and Williams⁴. Adam Tjepkema⁵ found a strong band at 1180-1160 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectra of several N^1N^4 disubstituted sulphonamides. Bexter⁶ *et al* made a somewhat detailed study of I.R. spectra of some sulphonamides. This has been followed by detailed I.R. studies of metal sulphonamide complexes by Chaturvedi and Kaushal⁷. Ueno and Martell^{8,9} have studied only the I.R. spectra of metal chelates of bisacetylaceton ethylene diamine and bis-salicylaldehyde ethylenediamine. Therefore in the present communication of the I.R. spectral data of sulphathiazole salicylaldimine

(SUTSA) and its metal chelates listed in Table 1 have been studied in the region 4000-625 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussions

The m.p.s are recorded in Table 1. The I.R. spectra of purified and dry substances were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer model-237 in nujol mull.

The spectral data of sulphathiazole salicylaldimine (I) and its Cu, Ag, Mn, Fe and Co complexes are given in Table 2.

As far as possible, assignments have been made to the various absorption bands in Table 2. The approximate intensities of different bands are also shown qualitatively by the commonly adopted symbols.

The molecule of sulphathiazole salicylaldimine (I) consists of salicylal, sulphanilamido (= $\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$) and thiazole groups.

Hence in the I.R. spectra of the ligand (I), characteristic absorption bands of these three groups are expected to be observed. In general this has been realised as is evident from the assignments given in Table 2. Some of the absorption bands of the ligand are expected to be modified or altered on chelation with metals. In addition the ligand itself shows some abnormal absorption bands.

The structure (I) of the ligand demands an absorption band near 3300 cm^{-1} for the -OH stretching but no such band is observed. This possibly may be due to hydrogen bonding of the salicylal group,

TABLE I

S. No.	Name	m.p. °C
1.	Sulphathiazole Salicylaldimine	228-9
2.	Cu—Sulphathiazole Salicylaldimine	230
3.	Ag—Sulphathiazole salicylaldimine	215 d
4.	Mn—Sulphathiazole salicylaldimine	208 d
5.	Fe—Sulphathiazole salicylaldimine	220
6.	Co—Sulphathiazole salicylaldimine	218 d

*Paper was read at 62nd Indian Science Congress Session, New Delhi; 3-5th Jan., 1975.

TABLE 2 INFRA RED ABSORPTION BANDS cm^{-1} OF SUTSA AND ITS METAL CHELATES

Ligand	Cu	Ag	Mn	Fe	Co	Assignments
3160	—	—	—	—	3160 m(Sh)	In the parent compound (i.e. ligand) bounded OH of the chelate of medium intensity, modified on chelation both in frequency and intensity. SO-NH-R stretch nujol absorption also (O-H stretching absorption) O-H stretching due to O-H...N type hydrogen bonding modified on chelation. Nujol absorptions 2852 ± 12 cm. chelated hydroxyl group and heterocyclic N-atom (B, 105) C = N absorption of the Schiff base, modified slightly on chelation (B, 146) (<i>Helv. Chim. Acta.</i> 1957, 40, 722 & 971) Overtone and combination bands of <i>p</i> -substituted benzene (W, 398) C = N stretch. —O = C—C = N asymmetrical stretch and chelation in ligand and also in the complexes (B., 144) (1619 ± 3) Six membered chelate and possibly aromatic aldimine frequency of the type Ar—CH = N—Ar as reported by Kiromann and Laurent for this group in Raman Spectra (W, 532) Possibly due to five membered thiazole ring, aromatic ring vibrations and anilino structure. Six membered heterocyclic ring (also in ligand), non-variant absorption band. Characteristic frequency of thiazole ring. C = N stretch and C = C stretching vibrations (B, 277)
3140	3135 w	3140 v.w. (Sh)	3140 v.w. (Sh)	3130 m.	3140 m.	
3100	3090 w	3100 v.w.	3100 v.w.	3080 m	3100 m	
3050 w	3050 w	—	—	3050 m	3050 m	
2960 v.c.	2950 v.s.	2950 v.s.	2945 v.s.	2945 v.s.	2950 v.s.	
2900 v.s.	2920 v.s.	2922 v.s.	2920 v.s.	2920 v.s.	2920 v.s.	
—	—	2864 v.s.	2866 v.s.	—	—	
2850 v.s.	2845 v.s.	2850 v.s.	2850 v.s.	2840 v.s.	2840 v.s.	
2640 m	—	—	—	—	2680 s	
2338 w	2320 v.w.	2300 v.w.	2300 v.w.	2318 v.w.	2630 s	
1900 v.w.	1900 v.w.	—	—	—	—	
1860 v.w.	1860 v.w.	—	—	—	1860 v.w.	
1680 v.w.	1680 v.w.	1680 v.w.	1680 v.w.	1680 v.w.	1680 v.w.	
1665 v.w.	—	1666 v.w.	1665 v.w.	1662 v.w.	1660 v.w.	
1620 s	1616 s	1622 s	1620 w	1622 s	1618 s	
1585 s	1590 s	1590 w	1590 m 1585 m	1594 m	1585 s	
1575 s	1580 s	1575 s	1575 s	1575 v.s.	1575 v.s.	
1570 s	1570 s 1560 m	1560 w	1560 w	1562 w	1560 s	
1538 v.s.	1538 v.s. 1530 v.s.	1535 v.s.	1540 v.s.	1538 v.s.	1537 v.s.	
—	1506 w	1515 w 1510 w	1510 v.w.	1510 m	1508 m	
1500 m	—	—	—	1500 m	1495 m	
1480 m	1490 m	1495 m	1490 m	1488 m	1485 m	
1468 v.s.	—	—	1468 v.s.	—	—	
1460 v.s.	1462 v.s. 1455	1462 v.s. 1450 v.s.	1460 v.s.	1462 s 1456 v.s.	1462 v.s. 1454 v.s.	
1420 s	1418 s	1420 w	1420 w	1420 w	1418 s	
1384 s	1380 s	1379 s	1382 s	1380 m	1380 v.s.	
1370 m	1368 m	1368 m	1368 m	1368 m	1366 s	
1346 m	1333 m	—	1345 m	1342 m	1342 m	
1314 v.s.	1323 s	1320 s	1320 m	1318 m	1318 s	
1308 s	1310 s	1308 w	1312 m	1308 s	1310 m	
—	—	1300 w	1300 w	1300 m	1300 s	
1290 m	1290 m	1290 m	1290 w	1288 s	1288 s	
1279 s	1272 m	1280 m 1278 m	1278 m	1260 w	1273 s	
1244 w	1237 v.w.	1247 v.w.	1245 v.w.	1245 v.w.	1243 v.w.	
1230 w	1220 v.w.	1220 v.w.	1220 v.w.	1228 v.w.	1225 w	
1190 m	—	—	—	1190 v.w.	—	
1174 w	1183 m 1170 w	1180 v.w. —	1185 w 1175 w	— 1178 w	1183 w 1178 w	
1152 v.s.	1145 v.s.	1168 w 1152 m	1152 s	1148 v.s.	1148 v.s.	
						Ring vibration (aromatic hydro carbon) Six membered chelate ring, also thiazole ring. nujol absorption. Aromatic C-H+stretching (K.K.C.) Six and five membered heterocyclic ring (possibly a combination frequency of six and five membered heterocyclic rings) $\frac{1400 + 1430}{2} = 1415$ SO — asymmetric stretch. Nujol absorption Possibly C-N stretch of the type Ar-N- (W, 572) SO ₂ -N frequency (Band I) Aromatic ring vibration and asymmetric SO ₂ -stretch. Possibly a combination frequency of M-N and M-O linkages. C-N stretching vibrations of aromatic* secondary amine. C-N stretch (Anilino) (W, 573) C-N stretch (Anilino) (W, 573) O-disubstituted phenyl Possibly phenolic OH absorption in ligand becomes very weak in Fe complex. Not observed in others (B, 110). SO -N frequency (Band II) Symmetrical SO ₂ -stretch similar to R-SO ₂ -R. (W, 550)

TABLE 2. INFRA RED ABSORPTION BANDS cm^{-1} OF SUTSA AND ITS METAL CHELATES (Contd.)

Ligand	Cu	Ag	Mn	Fe	Co	Assignments
1130 v.s.	1124 s	—	1135 m 1130 m	1135 m 1123 m	— 1128 s	o-Substituted benzene out of plane C-H deformation and SO_2 absorption.
1110 m 1100 s 1083 s	1104 w 1090 s 1078 m	1110 v.w. 1095 w 1082 m 1070 v.w.	1110 w 1095 w 1080 w	1110 w 1088 s — 1070 w	1110 m 1092 s 1080 s	
1038 w	1028 v.w.	—	—	1030 v.w.	1032 v.w.	S-O stretch similar to sulphoxides, (B, 359) also <i>o</i> -disubstituted phenyl ring.
1010 v.w.	1012 v.w.	1012- 1022 v.w.	1010- 1020 v.w.	1012 v.w.	1010 w	
—	990 v.w.	994 v.w.	—	985 v.w.	980 w	Possibly a combination frequency of C-N and M-O stretch $\frac{1290+680}{2}$.
978 v.w. 940 v.s. 912 w	973 v.w. 936 s 910 w	974 v.w. — —	975 v.w. 940 s 910 v.w.	970 v.w. 937 s 910 v.w.	975 w 935 v.s. 910 w	May be a combination frequency arising from aromatic vibrations and chelate ring. Aromatic ring vibrations
890 w 860 w	890 v.w. 860 s	— —	— 860 m	882 v.w. —	885 w 860 s	
850 s 845 s	— —	— —	— —	— —	855 s 845 s	Aromatic absorption, out of plane C-H bending vibrations. Hydrogen bonded out of plane OH bending vibration in ligand not observed in metal chelates except Co.
825 w	835 w	—	840 v.w. 838 w 825 v.w.	— 835 m —	840 s 822 w	1, 4 disubstituted benzene and C-H deformation. C-H bend, 1, 2 substitution in benzene ring.
780 w 762 s — 742 s	795 v.w. 776 v.w. 756 m — 740 m	— 778 v.w. 760 w — 738 w	— 780 v.w. 760 m 750 w 742 w 725 w 720 w	— 780 v.w. 760 m 750 w 740 m 725 m 720 m	— 778 w 760 s — 740 s	
— 709 s	725 w 708 m 698 m	720 w 712 v.w. 705 w	720 w — 705 w	710 v.w. 705 v.w.	720 w 705 s	
685 w	680 v.w.	684 v.w.	680 w	682 v.w.	680 v.w.	Ar-S linkage (B, 355)
666 m 642 v.v.s.	662 w 640 v.s.	667 w 640 s	665 w 645 s	660 w 642 s 637 s	662 w 640 s	N-H deformation of the chelated ligand and M-O linkage resulting in decreased intensity of bands. Chelate ring. Possibly ring deformation due to NH-bonding in ligand and M-N frequency in complexes.

B = Bellamy, W = Weisberger, Chemical Applications of Spectroscopy Interscience Publishers.

which will give resonance structures II and III to the ligand.

Due to chelation and hydrogen bonding OH absorptions are observed¹⁰ near 2600 cm^{-1} . We have observed an absorption band of medium intensity at 2640 cm^{-1} in the ligand. Our observations are supported by those of Ueno and Martell (*loc. cit.*) who have assigned an absorption band at 2600 cm^{-1} to OH stretching in bis-salicylaldehyde ethylenediamine^{9,10}. This band of 2640 cm^{-1} is not well

defined in Cu, Ag, Mn and Fe chelates but two bending absorptions at 2630 cm^{-1} and 2680 cm^{-1} of strong intensity are observed in Co-chelate.

Ueno and Martell (*loc. cit.*) have assigned an absorption of medium intensity at 1105 cm^{-1} in bis-salicylaldehyde ethylenediamine to C-O stretching of

hydrogen bonded ring system with corresponding bands of its metal chelates in the lower frequency region of 1090–1085 cm^{-1} . We have observed a strong absorption band at 1100 cm^{-1} in the ligand and corresponding bands of metal chelates in the frequency range of 1095 cm^{-1} –1088 cm^{-1} . The former is similarly assigned to C–O stretching vibrations of the hydrogen bonded ring system (II & III) of the ligand and the latter to C–O absorption in the metal chelates. The shift to lower frequency in metal chelates is probably due to the increased mass of the metal linked to oxygen as well as to possible weakening of C–O linkage as suggested by Ueno and Martell.

In the ligand two frequencies of medium intensity are observed at 3140 cm^{-1} and 3160 cm^{-1} indicating bonded OH group of the chelates. On metal chelation these are modified to a single frequency in the case of Cu, Ag, Mn, and Fe. In case of Co however no change in intensity or wave length of the absorption band is observed.

An absorption band at 3090 ± 10 cm^{-1} of varying intensity is observed in the ligand as also in the various chelates which is assigned to SO_2 -NH part of the molecule. This is in agreement with the observations of Chaturvedi and Kaushal¹¹⁻¹³ who have assigned similar absorption bands to SO_2 -NH-R stretching in the molecule of sulphonamide and some of the metal complexes of sulphanilamide. Thus there is a clear indication that the SO_2 -NH group of SUTSA is not involved in chelation.

An absorption band of very strong intensity at 2900 cm^{-1} is observed in the ligand which is ascribed to O–H–N type of hydrogen bonding¹⁴. On chelation the absorption band is modified to 2920 cm^{-1} in Cu, Mn, Fe and Co chelates (bivalent metals) where as in case of Ag-chelate (monovalent) it is modified to 2922 cm^{-1} . The intensity of absorption however remains unaltered.

A very weak absorption at 1662 ± 3 cm^{-1} is observed in the ligand as well as in the Ag, Mn, Fe and Co chelates. Possibly this is due to chelation in the ligand as well as in the complexes. However, it is suppressed in Cu-chelate.

Katrisky¹⁵ has discussed the data on I.R. absorption of hetero aromatic nucleus in various regions of the spectra and in the region of 1600–1350 cm^{-1} . He has shown that

- (i) for six membered hetero cyclic aromatic ring, absorption bands occur near 1605 cm^{-1} , 1575 cm^{-1} , 1480 cm^{-1} , and 1430 cm^{-1} and that these are relatively invariant but their intensities vary widely depending upon electronic nature of the substituent.
- (ii) five membered heterocyclic compounds generally showed three bands near 1590 cm^{-1} , 1490 cm^{-1} and 1400 cm^{-1} .

In the ligand of structure (I) there is hydrogen bonding and formation of six membered heterocyclic

ring so also in the chelates of structure (IV). Thus we should observe the frequencies for six membered heterocyclic ring as suggested by Katrisky (*loc. cit.*). This has been realised and the following frequencies have been observed—(a) 1619 ± 3 cm^{-1} , (b) 1575 cm^{-1} , (c) 1480 cm^{-1} , and (d) 1418 cm^{-1} , which possibly is a combination frequency arising from the characteristic frequencies for six and five membered heterocyclic rings, 1430 cm^{-1} and 1400 cm^{-1} respectively. Besides, there are absorption bands at 1585 ± 5 cm^{-1} of medium intensity pointing to the presence of a five membered heterocyclic ring i.e., the thiazole ring in the ligand (I) and the chelates (IV) and (V).

Absorption band of 720 cm^{-1} or 725 cm^{-1} of weak or medium intensity observed in the metal chelates only could possibly be assigned to a combination frequency arising from metal-oxygen (M-O) and metal-nitrogen (M-N) linkages. An absorption band at 680 ± 2 cm^{-1} is observed in the ligand as well as in the chelates, which could possibly be assigned to N–H deformation of the hydrogen bonded ligand and M=O linkage in the metal chelates. A band at 663 ± 3 cm^{-1} of medium intensity in the ligand and weak in the chelates is possibly due to chelation. Absorption band at 642 ± 2 cm^{-1} of strong intensity is observed in the ligand as also in the complexes. This could be assigned to ring deformation due to hydrogen bonding in the ligand and M–N frequency in the chelates.

All these observations finally support structure (IV) and (V) assigned to metal chelates. Similar structures have also been assigned by Maria Macrovicic¹⁶ and Mukherjee and Ray¹⁷ to some metal chelates of Schiff bases.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the Head of the Chemistry Department and the Principal for the facilities given and to Dr. K. P. Mishra (I.D.P.L.) for very kindly providing the I.R. spectra.

References

1. R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1974, 51, 385-86.
2. R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *Indore Univ. Res. J. Sci.* 1975, 3, 52.
3. SCHREIBER, *Analyt. Chem.* 1949, 21, 1168.
4. AUGUS LACTINE and WILLIAMS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.* 1951, 47, 1170.
5. R. ADAMS and J. J. TJEFKEMA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1948, 70, 4204.
6. J. N. BAXTOR, J. O. CRAIG and J. B. WILLIS, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1955, 669.
7. K. K. CHATURVEDI, Ph.D. thesis, 1971, Indore University.
8. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1955, 59, 998.

9. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1956, 60, 1270.
10. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infra red Spectra of Complex Molecules" John Wiley and Sons Inc. New-York, N. Y. 1954, p. 105.
11. K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *Indore Univ. Res. J. Sci.* 1972, 1, 56.
12. K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *Indore Univ. Res. J. Sci.* 1972 1, 66.
13. K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *Indore Univ. Res. J. Sci.* 1972, 1, 75.
14. D. J. C. YATES, N. SEPHARD and C. L. ANJER, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1955, 23, 1980.
15. KATRITSKY—*Quart. Rev.* 1959, 13, 358.
16. MARLA MACROVICI and COUST GH. MACROVICI. *Acad. rep. populare Romine Filiala Oluj, Studii Cercetari Stinti Ser.* 1955, 1, 115.
17. A. K. MUKHERJEA and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1955, 32, 604.